

STUDY OF THE CONTROL MODEL OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF CHEMICAL-TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Summary. In this thesis, various aspects of the modeling of chemical-technological processes are given. Various models of chemical production management have been studied.

In the modern world, process control is one of the key functions that determines the success and efficiency of production. Chemical-technological processes, in turn, are complex technological chains in which many conditions must be observed in order to obtain the desired result.

One of the important aspects of the process control model is the identification of key production parameters that need to be controlled and optimized. In chemical-technological processes, such parameters can be temperature, pressure, concentration, stirring speed, etc.

To control these parameters, various methods are used, such as sensors, measuring instruments and analytical methods. Modern production automation technologies allow you to automatically control production parameters and adjust them in real time.

Another important aspect of the process control model is the safety of production. Chemical processes can be hazardous to humans and the environment, so strict safety standards must be followed. To ensure the safety of production, various methods are used, such as emergency stop systems, equipment control and preventive maintenance systems, waste disposal and neutralization systems.

Another important aspect of the process control model is personnel management. The success of production directly depends on the qualifications and motivation of the staff. For personnel management, various methods are used, such as teaching and training methods, motivation and incentive systems, personnel assessment and development systems.

An important aspect of the process control model is risk management. Chemical processes may be associated with certain risks such as fires, explosions or releases of hazardous substances. Various methods are used to manage risks, such as risk analysis methods, methods for predicting and preventing emergencies, emergency warning and response systems, etc.

An important aspect of the process control model is the consideration of environmental aspects of production. In the chemical industry, production can have a negative impact on the environment. Various methods are used to take into account the environmental aspects of production, such as environmental assessment methods, systems for monitoring and collecting data on environmental impact, etc.

Concluding from the above, the process control model in the chemical industry is a complex and multi-aspect mechanism that includes many different aspects, such as production parameter control, product quality control systems, cost optimization, flexibility and adaptability, production safety, personnel management, management risks, taking into account environmental and social aspects of production, development and implementation of new technologies and taking into account international standards and requirements.

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